

Dr Bheemaiah, Anil Kumar, A.B Seattle W.A 98125
miyawaki@yopmail.com

Abstract:

Automation through blueprints and templates for the design of VUI is defined through machine evolution through machine DNA definitions for customization of template based designs, using code generators. Three taskoids are defined to enable the synthesis of wireframes and automated conversion to VUI designs from wireframes or screenshots. Examples from practical VUI frameworks like the Google Assistant and Amazon Alexa are presented, with a practical illustration of the algorithm using a screenshot from a popular website kayak.com. Future work entails non uniform tiling problem algorithms for wireframe composition, GAN based bitmap synthesis and cryption of VUI Template to machine DNA and transcription to VUI design JSON dumps. The positification() and optimism() directives in the C+ language (“[No Title]” n.d.) call for dialog management and modeling templates, to be defined in the context of taskoids in a future publication.

Keywords: Taskoids, Google Assistant, Amazon Alexa, VUI design automation, attnGAN, machine DNA

What: Low code Solutions to creating Taskoids from Web interaction diagrams using visual declarative programming.

How:

- Creating a wireframe from images.
- GAN models for generating the images.
- Composing images into widgets and DOM.
- Widgets vs image segmentation models.
- Conversion of DOM to VUI.
- VUI templates for a task.
- Encrypting VUI Template to machine DNA.
- Customized transcription of machine DNA to taskoid VUI.

Why:

Workoid futures can be purchased for a future date from a cloud service integration, for innovation management. At the end of the present product lifetime, there is a need for upgradation or a new solution. The new solution will involve the purchase of taskoid futures as workoids. Automation will enable the transcription of the purchased taskoid software from machine DNA to the required solution.

An example of the use of machine DNA transcription for customized taskoids is the service by Soul Machines for customized VUI. Here Digital DNA, a concept invented by Soul Machines is used to crypt

the design of digital humans, creating synthetic humans from transcribing digital DNA. Machine DNA™ is A.B's encrypting of a task, as quantized as a taskoid, atomicity of work. Combined with digital DNA, it can be transcribed for automation of a task or a set of related tasks by a digital human or a non-anthropomorphic cloud-based A.I program.

Summary:

Main Points:

- Definitions of the taskoids, TASSv1.0, TACv10, TACIv1.0
- Example of automated VUI Design from a screenshot of a kayak.com form.
- Automation of dialog management for VUI design.
- Automation of cloud functions from code search queries.

Applications:

Template based partial automation of VUI design using machine learning algorithms based on evolutionary computing.

Introduction.

Problem Definition.

TASSv1.0: Semantic Segmentation using FPN networks similar to Mapillary seamless segmentation algorithms(Bheemaiah, n.d.), to templates of object definitions, for creation of a DOM definition.

TACv10: Given [w], [r] and I, we consider many composition problems and synthesis problems for [w] and the tiling of [r] to I.

TACIv1.0: For a set of screenshots or wireframe images [ss], we define a mapping to a DOM structure, heuristic definitions and VUI

templates, [VUIT], with the creation of machine DNA and code generator based transcription to [[J],[L]], a set of intent, slot and entity based JSON Dump and a JSON or YAML dump of cloud functions.

Background.

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Formal Definitions:

Creating a wireframe from images: Screenshots for reverse engineering wireframes by semantic segmentation and image composition of wireframes from widget images are examples of taskoids for automated wireframe creation.

There exists the automation of creating VUI and VUI interfaces with media from the wireframes using a wireframe-object model generated by a taskoid automatically from the wireframe in target JS libraries like JQuery, RxJS, React or Angular, with a ready FaaS as microservice integration, with taskoids for green coding.

We consider the following taskoids.

TASSv1.0: Taskoid for semantic segmentation of screenshots or wireframe images, parsing, and backend on cloud.

TACv10: Taskoid for composing wireframes from individual images and automated backend.

TACiv1.0: Taskoid for VUI from a segmented or composed wireframe.

We consider the example of a set of screenshot images from the popular flight booking website kayak.com and create an AWS Conversations based template framework, for the automated generation of VUI intents and Lambda JSON dumps and YAML configurations, from the set of screenshots [ss].

Example of a SAM template for an AWS Lambda.

```
AWS::TemplateFormatVersion:
  '2010-09-09'
Transform:
  'AWS::Serverless-2016-10-31'
Resources:
  MyFunction:
    Type:
      'AWS::Serverless::Function'
    Properties:
      Handler: index.handler
      Runtime: nodejs6.10
      CodeUri:
        's3://my-bucket/function.zip'
```

(awslabs n.d.)

Semantic Segmentation of [ss] to [Om], defined for each template M.

We define a map \rightarrow [ss], [Om] for one or more images, [ss], where there exist many templates M, with object categories, [Om].

In this version, we assume a manual selection of templates and machine DNA representation of the object map as DNA, towards the creation of a map \rightarrow [Om],[VUIT],[[J],[L]] for a manual selection of the templates VUIT and creation of the intent JSON dumps, [J] and Lambda, JSON dumps [L].

An example from kayak.com

We use the same FPN based segmentation software as Mapillary, with a pre-trained network for each template M.

In a template we call 2DOM we can define an object mapping which is a DOM of the image screenshot with a payload of object definitions for all common widgets. We may define 2DOM.widgets = [menu, textBox, icon, radiobutton, list, bitmap, Date, button] for example. Further properties for each widget may be similarly defined as objects in segmentation. In the above example, the following widgets would be segmented, menu = [roundtrip, economy, adult], button = [search], textbox = [Minneapolis, ?, To] and Date = [Wed 11/17, Wed 11/20] and more categories.

A semantic map would entail the mapping of each of these objects in the DOM to intents, entities and slots for a JSON dump, for a VUI.

For example if the menu is considered, [roundtrip, adult, economy] then from the heuristic based VUI template, the menu entries are guessed as roundtrip = [roundtrip, oneway], adult = [No of adults, No of Children], economy = [economy, business]

This leads to a map to the JSON dump for the intents, slots and entities and actions for the information collected for the buttons defined, thus automating VUI generation.

While screenshot images can be used instead of wireframe designs, it is easy to compose wireframe designs as single bitmap images from constituent bitmap components. The taskoid TACv10 can be used for this purpose, with a library of bitmaps with tags and with scaling, it is a tiling problem of uniform or non uniform bitmaps into a desired bitmap image. There are ready algorithms for this problem in published literature. If there is a rectangular bound on a wireframe [w], then let [r] be the list of bounds. We then sequentially arrange in tiling an image I from [r]. In the case of uniform tiling by scaling, we compute the dimensions of any r, from the dimensions of I and size of [r] and use a linear algorithm for the tiling.

Non uniform tiling calls for a template based layout chosen using a heuristic based approach, which is a topic of a future publication.

Backend in cloud functions.

The backend is automatically computed to create the JSON dumps for cloud functions, similar to the SAM JSON representation described above. Code reuse calls for the creation of cloud function URIs similar to APIs for integration into coding similar to Bayou. (“Bayou: Program Synthesis Powered by Bayesian Machine Learning – Program Synthesis Powered by Bayesian Sketch Learning” n.d.; capergroup n.d.) , Given its open source, future work would

include the creation of search query based cloud function creation and integration, enabling back end automation.

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Discussion.

We have thus presented a taskoid based automation system for creating both wireframes from requirements and for the automated conversion of wireframes or screenshot images to VUI designs using templates. Both Google and Amazon are actively developing template based tools for dialog management, AWS Alexa Conversations is one such attempt, while Google has a mature framework with smalltalk for use in Dialog Flow. (“Template Actions for the Google Assistant” n.d.; TimmyMcCross 2017)

Future Work.

1. TASSv1.0: Given Bayou’s open source, (capergroup n.d.)future work would include the creation of search query based cloud function creation and integration, enabling back end automation.
2. TACv10: Non uniform tiling calls for a template based layout chosen using a heuristic based approach, which is a topic of a future publication.
3. TACiv1.0: Creation of [M] a template library, similar to that available in word processors and many low code visual declarative GUI.
4. Addition of GAN based synthesis of bitmaps for widgets from a symbolic textual description similar to attnGAN.(Xu et al. 2018)

5. (Xu et al. 2018)ent and templates, with several tools from A.B research, like CheapTalk and Unbias Coding(TM). (“[No Title]” n.d.)

References.

awslabs. n.d.

“Awslabs/serverless-Application-Model.” GitHub. Accessed October 21, 2019. <https://github.com/awslabs/serverless-application-model>.

“Bayou: Program Synthesis Powered by Bayesian Machine Learning – Program Synthesis Powered by Bayesian Sketch Learning.” n.d. Accessed October 21, 2019. <https://info.askbayou.com/>.

Bheemaiah, Anil Kumar. n.d. “Mapillary Based Plant Distributions of Ethnobotanical Afforestation.”

<https://doi.org/10.31224/osf.io/8nwfj>.

capergroup. n.d. “Capergroup/bayou.” GitHub. Accessed October 21, 2019.

<https://github.com/capergroup/bayou>.

“[No Title].” n.d. Accessed October 21, 2019a. <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/jswt9>.

———. n.d. Accessed October 21, 2019b. <http://vixra.org/pdf/1910.0166v1.pdf>.

“Template Actions for the Google Assistant.” n.d. Google Developers. Accessed October 21, 2019. <https://developers.google.com/assistant/templates>.

TimmyMcCross. 2017. “Dialog Management.” Medium. Bot Tutorials. July 20, 2017. <https://tutorials.botsfloor.com/dialog-management-799c20a39aad>.

Xu, Tao, Pengchuan Zhang, Qiuyuan Huang, Han Zhang, Zhe Gan, Xiaolei Huang, and Xiaodong He. 2018. “AttnGAN: Fine-Grained Text to Image Generation with Attentional Generative Adversarial

Networks.” *2018 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/cvpr.2018.00143>.

awslabs. n.d.

“Awslabs/serverless-Application-Model.” GitHub. Accessed October 21, 2019. <https://github.com/awslabs/serverless-application-model>.

“Bayou: Program Synthesis Powered by Bayesian Machine Learning – Program Synthesis Powered by Bayesian Sketch Learning.” n.d. Accessed October 21, 2019. <https://info.askbayou.com/>.